

Chemistry of N,S Donor Ligands : Synthesis and Spectral Characterisation of Thioazobenzene/Thioazomethine Mercury(II) Chloride

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Mercuric chloride reacts with thioazobenzene/thioazomethine in methanol under refluxing condition and orange products are isolated on slow evaporation. The compounds are five-membered N,S chelate having tetrahedral structure of $\text{Hg}(\text{N,S})\text{Cl}_2$.

There is a gradual increasing interest to define the coordination chemistry of N,S donor ligands¹. The transition and innertransition metals are mostly employed in this respect¹⁻³. Being a class b Lewis base S seeks soft metal to bind; Hg^{II} is one of the eligible members in this family and forms complexes of varying geometry and coordination number⁴. We have designed several NS/ONS donor ligands where S is thiol⁵ or thioether^{3,6,7} group, N- comes from azo or azomethine function and O- is phenolic. We reported earlier⁷ that mercury(II) in $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ encourages mercuriation at carbon centre leading to organometallic mercury compounds. Herein, we report synthesis and spectral characterisation of mercury(II) complexes of thioazobenzenes (1/2) and thioazomethines (3).

1a; R = Me, R' = H
b; R = R' = Me
c; R = Me, R' = Cl
2a; R = Et, R' = H
b; R = Et, R' = Me
c; R = Et, R' = Cl

3a; R = Me, R' = H
b; R = R' = Me
c; R = Me, R' = OMe
d; R = Me, R' = Cl
e; R = Me, R' = NO₂

Results and Discussion

Two classes of ligands, viz. 2-(alkylthio)azobenzenes (1/2)⁶ and 2-(alkylthio)azomethines (3)⁷ were synthesised by reported procedures. Mercury(II) complexes were synthesised by reacting HgCl_2 with the respective ligands. The complexes are numbered 4a-c, 5a-c and 6a-e (Table 1) which correspond to that prepared from ligands 1a-c, 2a-c and 3a-e respectively. Molecular conductance data show that the complexes are nonelectrolyte and elemental

analyses confirm 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio.

The electronic spectral data of the complexes have been recorded in MeOH. Thioazobenzenes (1/2) exhibit two main bands at 395 and 311 nm and a shoulder at 273 nm, which may be ascribed to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions⁸. In complexes 4 and 5, these bands are blue-shifted by 15–20 nm. Similar situation is exhibited by thioazomethines. The ligands 3 exhibit transitions around 280 and 350 nm, which are shifted to higher energy by 20–25 nm in complexes 6.

Complexes 4 and 5 show a sharp intense band at 1360–1380 cm^{-1} (N=N), which is red-shifted by 20–40 cm^{-1} from that of free ligand (1380–1400 cm^{-1}). Similarly the complexes (6) exhibit a sharp band at 1590–1610 cm^{-1} (C=N) which is red-shifted by 30–40 cm^{-1} from that of free ligand (1630–1640 cm^{-1}). The red-shifting supports azo/azomethine-N coordination^{3,6,9}. There is a possibility of five- or six-membered chelate ring constitution by azo-N coordination but small shift (20–40 cm^{-1}) in N=N stretching frequency compared to usual $\Delta\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$ 80–90 cm^{-1} for six-membered chelate ring⁹, supports five-membered ring structure^{10, 11}. This is also corroborated by ¹H nmr data (*vide infra*). The $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ mode of the ligand at 750–770 cm^{-1} is shifted to higher frequency by 30–40 cm^{-1} in the complexes, indicating Hg–S linkage^{3,9}. The medium intense band around 300 cm^{-1} (Hg–Cl) in the complexes is consistent with the frequencies normally associated with tetrahedral mercury(II)-halogen stretching modes^{11,12}. The stretch at 240–260 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{Hg-S}}$ mode. These results tentatively suggest the complexes are monomeric, four-coordinated and of tetrahedral geometry with N and S donor centres of ligands and two chlorines around mercury(II)^{11,13}.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the complexes (Table 1) have been compared with the spectra of ligands reported in literature^{6,7}. All aromatic proton signals of the complexes have been completely assigned on the basis of spin-spin structure and changes therein on substitution. The S-coordination is reflected from the downfield shifting of S–CH₃ (4, 6) or S–CH₂ (in S–Et) (5) signal by δ 0.2–0.3. Azomethine proton (CH=N) is shifted downfield by a small amount in 6 relative to free ligand 3. C-phenyl protons in

complexes **6** almost remain insensitive compared to free ligand (**3**) while thiophenyl ring protons suffer an appreciable downfield shifting. This indicates that metal coordination is confined to N,S donor systems in thioamine fragment. The substitution in C-phenyl ring has a little effect on the thiophenyl ring and affects only its parent ring protons. Similar argument is extended to Hg(thioazobenzene)Cl₂ (**4** and **5**) complexes. Comparison with the signals from free ligands suggests that thiophenyl ring protons are affected on complexation while other ring remains almost insensitive. Five-membered N,S chelate ring structure is thus established.

TABLE 1—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.	no	3-H ^a	4-H ^b	5-H ^b	6-H ^a	6'-H ^a	5'-H	4'-H	CH ₁	CH ₂	R
4a		7.70	7.58	7.55	8.08	7.85	7.47 ^b	7.47 ^b	2.78		
b		7.69	7.56	7.54	8.06	7.76	7.31 ^a		2.75		2.38
c		7.75	7.60	7.58	8.11	7.92	7.58 ^a		2.81		
5a		7.58	7.53	7.50	7.97	7.84	7.46 ^b	7.46 ^b	1.62	3.36	
b		7.56	7.50	7.48	7.96	7.75	7.29 ^a		1.60	3.34	2.48
c		7.65	7.56	7.54	8.00	7.95	7.59 ^a		1.64	3.38	
6a		7.35	7.32	7.32	7.38	8.01	7.68 ^b	7.68 ^b	2.69		
b		7.33	7.29	7.29	7.35	7.85	7.41 ^a		2.67		2.28
c		7.31	7.28	7.28	7.33	8.02	7.25 ^a		2.65		3.80
d		7.38	7.34	7.34	7.40	8.08	7.71 ^a		2.72		
e		7.42	7.37	7.37	7.45	8.16	8.40 ^a		2.80		

*J values not given as they are calculated from spectra not simulated.

^aDoublet. ^bTriplet.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) grade. The organic solvents were purified by standard methods. The elemental analysis was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (MeOH) on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker (200 MHz) FTNMR spectrometer. Conductance was measured on a Systronics 304 conductivity bridge.

2-(Alkylthio)azobenzenes⁶ (**1**, **2**) and 2-(alkylthio)-azomethines⁷ (**3**) were prepared by reported procedures. The mercuric(II) complexes were synthesised by reported procedure¹¹. To a methanolic solution (25 ml) of **1c** (0.5 g,

3.81 mmol) was added HgCl₂ (0.6 g, 2.21 mmol) in methanol. The reaction mixture was stirred and refluxed for 1 h and then evaporated slowly in air. The resulting orange compound (**4c**) was filtered and washed with cold methanol-water (1 : 1, v/v) mixture, yield 40%. Similarly, other complexes were prepared, yields 40–50%. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

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